

Comparisons of total power loss measurements performed by Epstein frame under operational temperatures

Draft A

Daniel Brunt¹, Adam Wilson¹, Graeme Finch¹, Stuart Harmon¹, Massimo Pasquale², Nicoleta Banu², Enzo Ferrara², Fausto Fiorillo², Ram Ramanathan Mathavan Jeyabalan³, Gaurang Vakil³

¹ National Physical Laboratory (NPL), United Kingdom

² Istituto Nazionale di Ricerca Metrologica (INRIM), Italy

³ University of Nottingham (UNOTT), United Kingdom

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1 Introduction

The transition towards electrification and greener technologies will see an unprecedented uptake in electrical machines, which will require machines with greater efficiencies to be designed and built. To achieve this a greater understanding of the magnetic materials is needed. It has long been known that the magnetic properties of materials are dramatically influenced by the operational conditions; frequency, temperature, and stress all play a significant role in determining the material's AC power loss and magnetic properties. As a consequence, there has been increasing industrial demand for representative material datasets. To facilitate this, the metrology and good practices associated with measurements made at operational conditions needs to be better defined to allow for future standardisation.

The measurement of specific total power loss in magnetic materials is enshrined within four International Standards covering three different geometries. These include Epstein frame at frequencies between 50 Hz and 400 Hz [1] and frequencies from 400 Hz to 10 kHz [2], Single Sheet Tester (SST) at power frequencies [3] and rings at frequencies from 20 Hz to 200 kHz [4]. One of the limitations of these standards is that the measurements described are all carried out at standard laboratory-based conditions at temperatures of $23\text{ °C} \pm 5\text{ °C}$. To date, no intercomparisons have been conducted for power loss at temperatures outside of room temperatures. The EMPIR HEFMAG (19ENG06) project was set up to develop the metrology covering all aspects related to the measurement of magnetic losses in electrical steels.

Within the HEFMAG project a new comparison was performed using Epstein frames up to temperatures of 155 °C and at frequencies up to 10 kHz. The aim of which is to develop and validate a traceability chain for measurements of power loss measurements at elevated temperatures.

As an output of the intercomparison, two documents will be drafted in parallel to the measurements. At all stages of the round robin test these documents shall reflect the current state of knowledge:

1. Report of measurement results: This document contains the results of measurements and their accuracy for each laboratory and a discussion of the findings during the intercomparison. This report will be shared through a report to IEC TC 68 and made available to the stakeholders.
2. A good practice guide on the measurement of power losses in non-oriented silicon-iron and cobalt-iron materials using the Epstein setups at elevated room temperature will be developed for end users. This document will provide the basis for discussions on CMC revisions and updates, and inform the development of future IEC 60404 standards produced by IEC TC 68 'Magnetic alloys and steels'.

2 Organisation

2.1 *Lead Laboratory*

National Physical Laboratory
Hampton Road
Teddington
United Kingdom
Phone: +44 20 8943 6908
e-mail: stuart.harmon@npl.co.uk

2.2 *Participants*

The following participated in the comparison:

Acronym	Laboratory	Country	Contact
INRIM	Istituto Nazionale di Ricerca Metrologica	Italy	Massimo Pasquale m.pasquale@inrim.it
NPL	National Physical Laboratory	United Kingdom	Daniel Brunt daniel.brunt@npl.co.uk Stuart Harmon stuart.harmon@npl.co.uk
UNOTT	University of Nottingham	United Kingdom	Gaurang Vakil Gaurang.Vakil@nottingham.ac.uk Ram Ramanathan Mathavan Jeyabalan Ram.Ramanathan@nottingham.ac.uk

2.3 *Comparison schedule*

The comparison was carried out by a circulation scheme. The organisation of the comparison follows: 1. INRIM, 2. NPL, 3. UNOTT and then the samples was returned to INRIM.

It was expected that each participant covers the freight charges from their location to the next on the list. Each participant was responsible for insurance of the samples from arrival in their laboratory until arrival in the subsequent laboratory.

The transport of the travelling standards was arranged by door-to-door parcel service.

3 Measurement instructions

3.1 Reference Samples

Two sets of Epstein strips were prepared for the comparison; one was a non-oriented (NO) silicon-iron (NO 0.2) and the other a cobalt-iron (CoFe 0.2). The thickness of strips in both sets is approximately 0.2 mm.

Measurements must be carried out such that the number of strips is a multiple of four. Additionally, the active mass of the test specimen should be at least 240 g for measurements at 400 Hz and below (according to IEC 60404-2) and no less than 12 strips for measurements above 400 Hz (according to IEC 60404-10).

Prior to measurements the samples were allowed to thermalise for at least 3 hours. All samples were demagnetised prior to measurement.

The measurement parameters used for each sample is given in

Table 1: Sample parameters used in power loss measurements.

Sample	Density (kg/m ³)	Cross section (× 10 ⁻⁵ m ²)	Weight (kg)	Number of strips, N_s	Nominal length (m)
NO 0.2	7650	2.89547	0.26576	20	0.300
		1.73397	0.15917	12	
FeCo 0.2	8120	3.5662	0.34755	24	0.300
		1.7834	0.1736	12	

3.2 Quantity to be measured

Measurements of the specific total power loss P_s (W/kg) of the Epstein samples were performed in general accordance to the standard IEC 60404-2 (up to 400 Hz) and IEC 60404-10 (above 400 Hz) using optimised experimental Epstein setups for power loss measurements up to temperatures of 155 °C.

3.3 Measurements of the samples

Each participant performed the measurements using their standard equipment and measurement procedures. The specific total losses were measured stepwise from the lowest to the highest peak polarisation value, J_p , at set frequencies as given in Tables 2 and 3. The measuring temperatures were 23 °C, 50 °C, 100 °C, 155 °C, with a target temperature tolerance ± 2 °C. If not, an appropriate correction of the temperature coefficient was applied.

Table 2: Measurement parameters for NO 0.2 Epstein sample at temperatures of 20 °C, 50 °C, 100 °C, and 155 °C.

Frequency (Hz)	Specific total power loss at J_p (T)
50	0.1, 0.15, 0.20, 0.35, 0.50, 1.0, 1.5
100	0.1, 0.15, 0.20, 0.35, 0.50, 1.0, 1.5
200	0.1, 0.15, 0.20, 0.35, 0.50, 1.0, 1.5
400	0.1, 0.15, 0.20, 0.35, 0.50, 1.0, 1.5
1000	0.10, 0.15, 0.20, 0.35, 0.50
2000	0.10, 0.15, 0.20, 0.35
5000	0.10, 0.15

Table 3: Measurement parameters for CoFe 0.2 Epstein sample at temperatures of 20 °C, 50 °C, 100 °C, and 155 °C.

Frequency (Hz)	Specific total power loss at J_p (T)
50	0.1, 0.15, 0.20, 0.35, 0.50, 1.0, 1.2, 1.5, 1.7, 2.0
400	0.1, 0.15, 0.20, 0.35, 0.50, 1.0, 1.2, 1.5, 1.7, 2.0
1000	0.10, 0.15, 0.20, 0.35, 0.50
2000	0.10, 0.15, 0.20, 0.35
5000	0.10, 0.15

4 Measurement results

4.1 Calculation of the reference value and its uncertainty

For all measurements of specific total power loss, the determination of the comparison reference value for this comparison was performed following procedure B in [5]. The Mandel-Paule (M-P) mean [6] was chosen for the analysis of the data. Based on these, the following characteristics were calculated:

- 1) The modified reduced observed chi-squared value by the formula:

$$\tilde{\chi}_{obs} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{(x_i - x_{ref})^2}{u_i^2}} \quad (1)$$

where N is the number of participants, x_i is the results of the total losses of the i -th participant of the comparisons and u_i is the declared standard uncertainty of the i -th participant of the comparison for a coverage factor $k = 1$ (68%).

- 2) The reference value of total losses x_{ref} by the formula:

$$x_{ref} = \mathbf{u}^2(x_{ref}) \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{x_i}{u_i^2} \quad (2)$$

- 3) The standard uncertainty of the reference value of total losses $u(x_{ref})$ by the formula:

$$\mathbf{u}(x_{ref}) = \left[\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{u_i^2} \right]^{-1/2} \quad (3)$$

- 4) The degree of equivalence of the measurement standard d_i by the formula (4) with a corresponding uncertainty by the formulas (5), (6):

$$d_i = x_i - x_{ref} \quad (4)$$

$$u(d_i) = \sqrt{u^2(x_i) + u^2(x_{ref})} \quad (5)$$

$$E_n = \frac{|d_i|}{2u(d_i)}, \quad (6)$$

where d_i is degree of equivalence and $u(d_i)$ is the standard uncertainty of the degree of equivalence. The declared uncertainties are judged as reliable if equation $E_n < 1$ is satisfied.

4.2 Comparison results

4.2.1 Nippon NO 0.2 mm Results

The individual power loss values and the average values (calculated as described in Section 4.1) for INRIM and NPL for 32 strips of Nippon NO 0.2 mm Silicon-iron carried out at temperatures of 23 °C, 50 °C, 100 °C and 155 °C are given in Tables 4, 5, 6 and 7 respectively.

The individual power loss values and the average values for INRIM and NPL for 16 strips of Nippon NO 0.2 mm Silicon-iron carried out at temperatures of 23 °C, 50 °C, 100 °C and 155 °C are given in Tables 8 to 13.

4.2.2 VAC CoFe 0.2 mm Results

The individual power loss values and the average values (calculated as described in Section 4.1) for INRIM and NPL for 24 strips of VAC CoFe 0.2 mm out at temperatures of 23 °C, 50 °C, 100 °C and 155 °C are given in Tables 14 and 15.

The individual power loss values and the average values for INRIM and NPL for 12 strips of VAC CoFe 0.2 mm out at temperatures of 23 °C, 50 °C, 100 °C and 155 °C are given in Tables 16 to 19.

Table 4: Comparison results for NO 0.2 using 32 strips at 23 °C.

N_s	T (°C)	f (Hz)	J (T)	LAB 1		LAB 2		x_{ref} (W/kg)	$u(x_{ref})$ (W/kg)	E_n	
				X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$			LAB 1	LAB 2
32	23	50	0.1	0.01307	1	0.0134	0.75	0.0133	0.60	0.627	0.421
			0.2	0.05789	0.5	0.0580	0.35	0.0580	0.29	0.095	0.059
			0.5	0.29888	0.5	0.2984	0.35	0.2985	0.29	0.103	0.064
			1	0.94415	0.35	0.9508	0.50	0.9463	0.29	0.254	0.406
			1.5	2.24425	0.45	2.256	0.50	2.2493	0.33	0.201	0.231
		100	0.1	0.02827	1.25	0.0287	0.75	0.0286	0.64	0.369	0.187
			0.15	0.06763	0.5	0.0692	0.50	0.0684	0.35	0.965	0.950
			0.2	0.12403	0.5	0.1244	0.3	0.1243	0.26	0.221	0.113
			0.35	0.35192	0.5	0.3530	0.3	0.3527	0.26	0.195	0.100
			0.5	0.65290	0.5	0.6509	0.3	0.6514	0.26	0.200	0.103
			1	2.07934	0.5	2.0904	0.50	2.0849	0.35	0.218	0.217
			1.5	4.90178	0.45	4.9663	0.45	4.9341	0.32	0.596	0.591
		200	0.1	0.06443	1	0.0648	0.75	0.0647	0.60	0.153	0.104
			0.15	0.15363	0.5	0.1560	0.5	0.1548	0.35	0.620	0.614
			0.2	0.27799	0.5	0.2800	0.35	0.2793	0.29	0.417	0.259
			0.35	0.79488	0.5	0.8021	0.3	0.8002	0.26	0.590	0.300
			0.5	1.48653	0.5	1.4908	0.45	1.4889	0.33	0.133	0.115
			1	4.78030	0.5	4.8532	0.5	4.8168	0.35	0.621	0.615
		400	0.1	0.15210	1	0.1571	0.75	0.1553	0.60	0.905	0.605
			0.15	0.36028	1	0.3746	1	0.3675	0.71	0.808	0.787
0.2	0.65755		0.5	0.6710	0.5	0.6643	0.35	0.834	0.823		
0.35	1.89800		0.5	1.9315	0.55	1.9132	0.37	0.641	0.719		
0.5	3.56473		0.55	3.6313	0.55	3.5980	0.39	0.691	0.683		

Table 5: Comparison results for NO 0.2 using 32 strips at 50 °C.

N_s	T (°C)	f (Hz)	J (T)	LAB 1		LAB 2		x_{ref} (W/kg)	$u(x_{ref})$ (W/kg)	E_n	
				X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$			LAB 1	LAB 2
32	50	50	0.1	0.01289	1	0.0133	0.75	0.0132	0.60	0.873	0.583
			0.15	0.03186	0.5	0.0321	0.5	0.0320	0.35	0.310	0.308
			0.2	0.05729	0.5	0.0575	0.3	0.0575	0.26	0.252	0.129
			0.35	0.16189	0.5	0.1620	0.3	0.1620	0.26	0.064	0.033
			0.5	0.29670	0.5	0.2966	0.3	0.2967	0.26	0.011	0.006
			1	0.94110	0.35	0.9473	0.5	0.9432	0.29	0.241	0.384
			1.5	2.20066	0.45	2.2280	0.7	2.2086	0.38	0.308	0.546
		100	0.1	0.02808	1	0.0287	0.75	0.0285	0.60	0.579	0.390
			0.15	0.06797	0.5	0.0689	0.5	0.0685	0.35	0.588	0.582
			0.2	0.12375	0.75	0.1238	0.3	0.1238	0.28	0.021	0.006
			0.35	0.34947	0.5	0.3507	0.3	0.3504	0.26	0.232	0.119
			0.5	0.64672	0.5	0.6469	0.3	0.6469	0.26	0.022	0.011
			1	2.06287	0.35	2.0805	0.5	2.0687	0.29	0.310	0.493
			1.5	4.83593	0.45	4.9039	0.5	4.8663	0.33	0.560	0.638
		200	0.1	0.06383	1	0.0645	0.85	0.0642	0.65	0.267	0.213
			0.15	0.15387	0.5	0.1544	0.6	0.1541	0.38	0.103	0.131
			0.2	0.27901	0.5	0.2770	0.45	0.2779	0.33	0.324	0.283
			0.35	0.78913	0.5	0.7944	0.3	0.7930	0.26	0.433	0.221
			0.5	1.47010	0.5	1.4786	0.3	1.4763	0.26	0.377	0.192
			1	4.73827	0.5	4.8305	0.5	4.7844	0.35	0.792	0.782
			400	0.1	0.14969	1	0.1554	0.8	0.1532	0.62	0.981
		0.15		0.36133	1	0.3691	0.55	0.3673	0.48	0.740	0.335
		0.2		0.64743	0.5	0.6610	0.55	0.6536	0.37	0.762	0.853
		0.35		1.87545	0.5	1.9088	0.55	1.8906	0.37	0.646	0.724
0.5	3.52373	0.55		3.5933	0.55	3.5585	0.39	0.730	0.720		

Table 6: Comparison results for NO 0.2 using 32 strips at 100 °C.

N_s	T (°C)	f (Hz)	J (T)	LAB 1		LAB 2		x_{ref} (W/kg)	$u(x_{ref})$ (W/kg)	E_n	
				X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$			LAB 1	LAB 2
32	100	50	0.1	0.01339	1	0.0138	0.8	0.0137	0.62	0.820	0.597
			0.15	0.03222	0.5	0.0330	0.55	0.0326	0.37	0.840	0.939
			0.2	0.05800	0.5	0.0586	0.35	0.0584	0.29	0.578	0.358
			0.5	0.29755	0.5	0.3000	0.3	0.2993	0.26	0.533	0.271
			1	0.95085	0.35	0.9567	0.3	0.9542	0.23	0.423	0.343
			1.5	2.16847	0.45	2.1983	0.65	2.1781	0.37	0.381	0.614
		100	0.1	0.02858	1	0.0293	0.75	0.0291	0.60	0.711	0.477
			0.15	0.06916	0.5	0.0697	0.55	0.0694	0.37	0.301	0.340
			0.2	0.12370	0.5	0.1246	0.3	0.1244	0.26	0.490	0.250
			0.5	0.64488	0.5	0.6496	0.3	0.6483	0.26	0.476	0.243
			1	2.06323	0.35	2.0886	0.5	2.0716	0.29	0.447	0.709
			1.5	4.73292	0.45	4.8177	0.5	4.7708	0.33	0.713	0.810
		200	0.1	0.06283	1	0.0652	1	0.0640	0.71	0.779	0.759
			0.15	0.15200	0.5	0.1552	0.5	0.1536	0.35	0.856	0.844
			0.2	0.27415	0.5	0.2781	0.3	0.2770	0.26	0.937	0.475
			0.35	0.78595	0.5	0.7951	0.3	0.7927	0.26	0.760	0.386
			0.5	1.45928	0.35	1.4782	0.3	1.4702	0.23	0.892	0.720
			1	4.69964	0.6	4.8141	0.6	4.7569	0.42	0.825	0.812
		400	0.1	0.14758	1	0.1545	1	0.1510	0.71	0.952	0.923
			0.15	0.35480	1	0.3665	1	0.3606	0.71	0.669	0.655
			0.2	0.63793	1	0.6565	1	0.6472	0.71	0.591	0.580
			0.35	1.85645	0.5	1.8953	0.55	1.8740	0.37	0.759	0.849
			0.5	3.47341	0.6	3.5666	0.6	3.5200	0.42	0.909	0.893

Table 7: Comparison results for NO 0.2 using 32 strips at 155 °C.

N_s	T (°C)	f (Hz)	J (T)	LAB 1		LAB 2		x_{ref} (W/kg)	$u(x_{ref})$ (W/kg)	E_n	
				X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$			LAB 1	LAB 2
32	155	50	0.1	0.01350	1	0.0139	0.8	0.0138	0.62	0.838	0.610
			0.15	0.03245	0.5	0.0330	0.55	0.0327	0.37	0.587	0.660
			0.2	0.05813	0.5	0.0589	0.35	0.0586	0.29	0.725	0.449
			0.35	0.16727	0.5	0.1643	0.5	0.1658	0.35	0.735	0.744
			0.5	0.30025	0.5	0.3007	0.35	0.3006	0.29	0.097	0.060
			1	0.95091	0.35	0.9571	0.5	0.9529	0.29	0.237	0.378
			1.5	2.10953	0.45	2.1376	0.5	2.1221	0.33	0.530	0.605
		100	0.1	0.02826	1.1	0.0296	1.1	0.0289	0.78	0.902	0.873
			0.15	0.06859	0.5	0.0701	0.5	0.0693	0.35	0.894	0.882
			0.2	0.12331	0.5	0.1252	0.3	0.1247	0.26	0.974	0.493
			0.35	0.34975	0.5	0.3525	0.3	0.3518	0.26	0.516	0.263
			0.5	0.64420	0.5	0.6487	0.3	0.6475	0.26	0.452	0.230
			1	2.05668	0.35	2.0791	0.45	2.0651	0.28	0.459	0.637
			1.5	4.58749	0.45	4.6713	0.45	4.6294	0.32	0.826	0.816
		200	0.1	0.06373	1	0.0654	0.8	0.0648	0.62	0.689	0.503
			0.15	0.15223	0.5	0.1545	0.55	0.1533	0.37	0.539	0.606
			0.2	0.27402	0.5	0.2763	0.35	0.2756	0.29	0.491	0.305
			0.35	0.78508	0.5	0.7894	0.35	0.7880	0.29	0.318	0.198
			0.5	1.45414	0.35	1.4657	0.35	1.4599	0.25	0.462	0.459
			1	4.67019	0.5	4.7628	0.5	4.7165	0.35	0.807	0.797
		400	0.1	0.14736	1	0.1542	1	0.1508	0.71	0.941	0.913
			0.15	0.35328	1	0.3638	0.75	0.3600	0.60	0.816	0.546
			0.2	0.63443	0.55	0.6512	0.55	0.6428	0.39	0.977	0.960
			0.35	1.83660	0.5	1.8743	0.55	1.8537	0.37	0.744	0.834
0.5	3.44058		0.5	3.5214	0.55	3.4771	0.37	0.851	0.951		

Table 8: Comparison results for NO 0.2 using 16 strips at 23 °C and at frequencies between 50 Hz and 200 Hz.

N_s	T (°C)	f (Hz)	J (T)	LAB 1		LAB 2		x_{ref} (W/kg)	$u(x_{ref})$ (W/kg)	E_n	
				X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$			LAB 1	LAB 2
16	23	50	0.1	0.01280	1	0.0127	0.70	0.0127	0.57	0.262	0.165
			0.15	0.03158	0.5	0.0311	0.60	0.0314	0.38	0.476	0.613
			0.2	0.05731	0.5	0.0561	0.55	0.0568	0.37	0.752	0.866
			0.35	0.16353	0.6	0.1594	0.60	0.1614	0.42	0.868	0.883
			0.5	0.30086	0.6	0.2931	0.60	0.2970	0.42	0.879	0.894
			1	0.96029	0.5	0.9384	0.50	0.9494	0.35	0.933	0.947
			1.5	2.23013	1	2.2077	0.50	2.2122	0.45	0.368	0.151
		100	0.1	0.02786	0.5	0.0273	0.8	0.0277	0.42	0.428	0.805
			0.15	0.06800	0.5	0.0664	0.6	0.0674	0.38	0.758	0.982
			0.2	0.12310	0.55	0.1200	0.55	0.1216	0.39	0.926	0.941
			0.35	0.35323	0.55	0.3444	0.55	0.3488	0.39	0.937	0.953
			0.5	0.65504	0.55	0.6378	0.55	0.6464	0.39	0.979	0.997
			1	2.10208	0.5	2.0587	0.55	2.0825	0.37	0.752	0.866
		200	0.1	0.06253	1	0.0622	0.5	0.0623	0.45	0.174	0.071
			0.15	0.15129	0.5	0.1507	0.45	0.1510	0.33	0.181	0.158
			0.2	0.27433	0.5	0.2720	0.45	0.2730	0.33	0.395	0.345
			0.35	0.79628	0.5	0.7835	0.45	0.7892	0.33	0.740	0.650
			0.5	1.49020	0.5	1.4622	0.45	1.4747	0.33	0.867	0.763
			1	4.83176	0.5	4.7656	0.45	4.7952	0.33	0.630	0.553
			1.5	11.1492	0.45	11.2424	0.45	11.1958	0.32	0.379	0.377

Table 9: Comparison results for NO 0.2 using 16 strips at 23 °C and at frequencies between 400 Hz and 5000 Hz.

N_s	T (°C)	f (Hz)	J (T)	LAB 1		LAB 2		x_{ref} (W/kg)	$u(x_{\text{ref}})$ (W/kg)	E_n	
				X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$			LAB 1	LAB 2
16	23	400	0.1	0.15049	1	0.1511	0.45	0.1510	0.41	0.163	0.059
			0.15	0.36273	1	0.3610	0.45	0.3613	0.41	0.185	0.067
			0.2	0.65468	0.5	0.6492	0.45	0.6516	0.33	0.386	0.337
			0.35	1.89052	0.5	1.8812	0.45	1.8854	0.33	0.225	0.197
			0.5	3.57972	0.35	3.5473	0.45	3.5675	0.28	0.383	0.538
			1	11.80866	0.35	11.7844	0.45	11.7995	0.28	0.087	0.122
		1000	0.1	0.54700	0.5	0.5416	1.05	0.5460	0.45	0.135	0.353
			0.15	1.27130	0.5	1.2679	1.05	1.2707	0.45	0.037	0.097
			0.2	2.27805	0.5	2.2644	1.05	2.2755	0.45	0.082	0.214
			0.35	6.58946	0.5	6.5822	1.05	6.5881	0.45	0.015	0.039
			0.5	12.49436	0.35	12.5507	1.05	12.5000	0.33	0.047	0.184
		2000	0.1	1.58434	1	1.5896	1.05	1.5868	0.72	0.064	0.068
			0.15	3.61364	1	3.6304	1.05	3.6216	0.72	0.089	0.095
			0.2	6.38482	0.5	6.4058	1.05	6.3887	0.45	0.045	0.117
			0.35	17.80815	1	18.3813	1.05	18.0808	0.72	0.617	0.644
		5000	0.1	6.91010	1	7.1598	1.05	7.0289	0.72	0.692	0.721
			0.15	15.15841	1.7	16.3783	1.7	15.7684	1.20	0.953	0.905

Table 10: Comparison results for NO 0.2 using 16 strips at 50 °C and at frequencies between 50 Hz and 200 Hz.

N_s	T (°C)	f (Hz)	J (T)	LAB 1		LAB 2		x_{ref} (W/kg)	$u(x_{\text{ref}})$ (W/kg)	E_n	
				X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$			LAB 1	LAB 2
16	50	50	0.1	0.01265	1	0.0127	0.65	0.0127	0.54	0.062	0.035
			0.15	0.03110	1	0.0311	0.5	0.0311	0.45	0.039	0.016
			0.2	0.05628	1	0.0558	0.5	0.0559	0.45	0.340	0.140
			0.35	0.16010	0.5	0.1586	0.5	0.1593	0.35	0.393	0.396
			0.5	0.29455	0.35	0.2915	0.45	0.2934	0.28	0.440	0.618
			1	0.94345	0.35	0.9343	0.45	0.9400	0.28	0.412	0.579
			1.5	2.19968	0.5	2.1788	0.45	2.1882	0.33	0.436	0.381
		100	0.1	0.02668	1	0.0275	0.75	0.0272	0.60	0.890	0.595
			0.15	0.06663	1	0.0669	0.5	0.0669	0.45	0.156	0.064
			0.2	0.12035	0.5	0.1206	0.5	0.1205	0.35	0.081	0.081
			0.35	0.34575	0.5	0.3436	0.45	0.3446	0.33	0.288	0.251
			0.5	0.64030	0.35	0.6353	0.45	0.6384	0.28	0.333	0.468
			1	2.06078	0.35	2.0487	0.45	2.0562	0.28	0.247	0.346
			1.5	4.82208	0.5	4.7903	0.45	4.8045	0.33	0.303	0.265
		200	0.1	0.06033	1	0.0621	0.75	0.0615	0.60	0.821	0.549
			0.15	0.15023	0.5	0.1500	0.5	0.1501	0.35	0.058	0.058
			0.2	0.27183	0.5	0.2700	0.5	0.2709	0.35	0.268	0.270
			0.35	0.78290	0.5	0.7768	0.5	0.7799	0.35	0.316	0.318
			0.5	1.46886	0.5	1.4490	0.5	1.4589	0.35	0.554	0.559
			1	4.75177	0.5	4.7270	0.5	4.7394	0.35	0.213	0.214
			1.5	11.07067	0.45	11.0863	0.45	11.0785	0.32	0.064	0.064

Table 11: Comparison results for NO 0.2 using 16 strips at 50 °C and at frequencies between 400 Hz and 5000 Hz.

N_s	T (°C)	f (Hz)	J (T)	LAB 1		LAB 2		x_{ref} (W/kg)	$u(x_{\text{ref}})$ (W/kg)	E_n	
				X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$			LAB 1	LAB 2
16	50	400	0.1	0.135429	2.4	0.1506	2.4	0.1430	1.70	0.933	0.869
			0.15	0.335193	1.5	0.3595	1.5	0.3473	1.06	0.973	0.929
			0.2	0.614967	1.1	0.6458	1.1	0.6304	0.78	0.921	0.892
			0.35	1.831728	0.5	1.8679	0.5	1.8498	0.35	0.804	0.794
			0.5	3.53375	0.5	3.5183	0.5	3.5260	0.35	0.178	0.179
			1	11.50703	0.35	11.6824	0.5	11.5647	0.29	0.553	0.876
		1000	0.1	0.513171	1	0.5333	1.05	0.5227	0.72	0.751	0.781
			0.15	1.21372	0.75	1.2482	1.05	1.2254	0.61	0.494	0.755
			0.2	2.16792	0.75	2.2303	1.05	2.1890	0.61	0.501	0.766
			0.35	6.35080	0.5	6.4915	1.05	6.3768	0.45	0.303	0.775
			0.5	12.10505	0.35	12.3792	1.05	12.1325	0.33	0.234	0.906
		2000	0.1	1.49927	1	1.5579	1.05	1.5272	0.72	0.748	0.778
			0.15	3.44275	1	3.5626	1.05	3.4997	0.72	0.667	0.695
			0.2	6.07425	1	6.2932	1.05	6.1784	0.72	0.690	0.719
			0.35	17.49075	1	18.0944	1.05	17.7779	0.72	0.661	0.690
		5000	0.1	6.74493	1	7.0019	1.05	6.8672	0.72	0.729	0.759
			0.15	14.87150	1	15.5083	1.05	15.1744	0.72	0.819	0.850

Table 12: Comparison results for NO 0.2 using 16 strips at 100 °C and at frequencies between 400 Hz and 5000 Hz.

N_s	T (°C)	f (Hz)	J (T)	LAB 1		LAB 2		x_{ref} (W/kg)	$u(x_{\text{ref}})$ (W/kg)	E_n	
				X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$			LAB 1	LAB 2
16	100	400	0.1	0.13838	1.6	0.1489	1.6	0.1436	1.13	0.957	0.911
			0.15	0.33825	1	0.3538	1	0.3460	0.71	0.932	0.905
			0.2	0.61382	1	0.6366	1	0.6252	0.71	0.754	0.736
			0.35	1.80737	0.5	1.8474	0.5	1.8274	0.35	0.901	0.887
			0.5	3.41560	0.5	3.4821	0.5	3.4488	0.35	0.792	0.782
			1	11.38061	0.35	11.5562	0.5	11.4384	0.29	0.560	0.887
		1000	0.1	0.498874	1.5	0.5345	1.5	0.5167	1.06	0.960	0.917
			0.15	1.181140	1.2	1.2469	1.2	1.2140	0.85	0.938	0.905
			0.2	2.119100	1.2	2.2272	1.2	2.1731	0.85	0.860	0.832
			0.35	6.233880	1	6.4753	1.05	6.3487	0.72	0.741	0.771
			0.5	11.943005	1	12.3356	1.05	12.1298	0.72	0.630	0.658
		2000	0.1	1.435510	1.7	1.5492	1.7	1.4924	1.20	0.939	0.892
			0.15	3.329791	1.5	3.5479	1.5	3.4389	1.06	0.882	0.845
			0.2	5.873598	1.5	6.2708	1.5	6.0722	1.06	0.910	0.871
			0.35	17.103215	1.1	18.0180	1.1	17.5606	0.78	0.984	0.950
		5000	0.1	6.44799	1.8	7.0127	1.8	6.7303	1.27	0.979	0.925
			0.15	14.33441	1.5	15.2800	1.5	14.8072	1.06	0.888	0.851

Table 13: Comparison results for NO 0.2 using 16 strips at 155 °C and at frequencies between 50 Hz and 5000 Hz.

N_s	T (°C)	f (Hz)	J (T)	LAB 1		LAB 2		x_{ref} (W/kg)	$u(x_{ref})$ (W/kg)	E_n	
				X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$			LAB 1	LAB 2
16	155	50	0.5	0.295714	0.5	0.2959	0.45	0.2958	0.33	0.031	0.027
			1	0.947738	0.5	0.9460	0.45	0.9468	0.33	0.085	0.074
			1.5	2.087020	1	2.0913	0.45	2.0906	0.41	0.079	0.028
		100	0.5	0.635638	0.35	0.6375	0.45	0.6364	0.28	0.127	0.176
			1	2.046844	0.35	2.0500	0.45	2.0480	0.28	0.065	0.091
			1.5	4.538367	0.5	4.5634	0.45	4.5522	0.33	0.253	0.219
		200	0.5	1.432067	0.35	1.4372	0.45	1.4340	0.28	0.151	0.211
			1	4.666083	0.35	4.6797	0.45	4.6712	0.28	0.124	0.172
		400	0.1	0.137370	1.8	0.1487	1.8	0.1430	1.27	0.923	0.875
			0.15	0.331057	1.4	0.3524	1.4	0.3417	0.99	0.928	0.891
			0.2	0.603656	1	0.6325	1	0.6181	0.71	0.967	0.938
			0.35	1.778386	0.7	1.8291	0.7	1.8038	0.49	0.828	0.813
			0.5	3.400150	0.5	3.4412	0.5	3.4207	0.35	0.491	0.488
			1	11.208436	0.35	11.3793	0.5	11.2646	0.29	0.553	0.876
		1000	0.1	0.4916308	1	0.5114	1.05	0.5010	0.72	0.770	0.801
			0.15	1.1682667	0.5	1.1965	1.05	1.1735	0.45	0.331	0.844
			0.5	11.6994633	0.35	11.9613	1.05	11.7256	0.33	0.232	0.896
		2000	0.1	1.4225667	1	1.4674	1.05	1.4439	0.72	0.605	0.632
			0.15	3.2633500	0.75	3.3657	1.05	3.2979	0.61	0.546	0.833
		5000	0.1	6.3009775	1	6.4959	1.05	6.3937	0.72	0.593	0.620
			0.15	13.9510167	0.8	14.4793	1.05	14.1451	0.64	0.677	0.946

Table 14: Comparison results for CoFe 0.2 using 24 strips at 23 °C and 50 °C and at a frequency of 50 Hz.

N_s	T (°C)	f (Hz)	J (T)	LAB 1		LAB 2		x_{ref} (W/kg)	$u(x_{\text{ref}})$ (W/kg)	E_n	
				X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$			LAB 1	LAB 2
24	23	50	0.1	0.02073	1.5	0.0196	1.5	0.0202	1.06	0.747	0.775
			0.15	0.04553	1.5	0.0426	1.5	0.0441	1.06	0.887	0.927
			0.2	0.07668	1.6	0.0712	1.6	0.0739	1.13	0.918	0.964
			0.5	0.32489	1.9	0.2982	1.9	0.3116	1.34	0.894	0.947
			1	0.88217	2.2	0.7956	2.2	0.8389	1.56	0.926	0.992
			1.2	1.13053	1.7	1.0462	1.7	1.0884	1.20	0.907	0.955
			1.5	1.58415	1.5	1.5004	1.5	1.5423	1.06	0.726	0.753
			1.7	1.93132	1.5	1.8433	1.5	1.8873	1.06	0.625	0.645
			2	2.39392	1	2.3246	1	2.3592	0.71	0.594	0.606
	50	50	0.1	0.02207	2.2	0.0199	2.2	0.0210	1.56	0.917	0.982
			0.15	0.04936	2.4	0.0441	2.4	0.0467	1.70	0.916	0.986
			0.2	0.07488	2.4	0.0743	2.4	0.0746	1.70	0.064	0.065
			0.5	0.35257	2.7	0.3114	2.7	0.3320	1.91	0.900	0.977
			1	0.91946	2.2	0.8324	2.2	0.8759	1.56	0.893	0.954
			1.2	1.18575	1.7	1.0966	1.7	1.1412	1.20	0.914	0.963
			1.5	1.67379	1.5	1.5675	1.5	1.6207	1.06	0.873	0.912
			1.7	2.01032	1.2	1.9047	1.2	1.9575	0.85	0.902	0.935
			2	2.45688	1.2	2.3686	1.2	2.4128	0.85	0.615	0.630

Table 15: Comparison results for CoFe 0.2 using 24 strips at 100 °C and 155 °C and at a frequency of 50 Hz.

N_s	T (°C)	f (Hz)	J (T)	LAB 1		LAB 2		x_{ref} (W/kg)	$u(x_{\text{ref}})$ (W/kg)	E_n	
				X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$			LAB 1	LAB 2
24	100	50	0.1	0.02330	2.2	0.0211	2.2	0.0222	1.56	0.886	0.946
			0.15	0.05220	2.4	0.0468	2.4	0.0495	1.70	0.890	0.956
			0.2	0.08745	2.4	0.0785	2.4	0.0830	1.70	0.886	0.952
			0.5	0.36681	2.6	0.3248	2.6	0.3458	1.84	0.916	0.993
			1	0.95918	2	0.8767	2	0.9179	1.41	0.890	0.945
			1.2	1.26144	2	1.1614	2	1.2114	1.41	0.820	0.866
			1.5	1.79967	2	1.6554	2	1.7275	1.41	0.829	0.877
			1.7	2.12558	1.5	1.9918	1.5	2.0587	1.06	0.865	0.904
			2	2.55164	1	2.4394	1	2.4955	0.71	0.904	0.932
	155	50	0.1	0.02268	2	0.0216	2	0.0221	1.41	0.507	0.525
			0.15	0.05008	2	0.0475	2	0.0488	1.41	0.540	0.559
			0.2	0.08429	2	0.0793	2	0.0818	1.41	0.614	0.639
			0.5	0.36130	2.2	0.3269	2.2	0.3441	1.56	0.897	0.959
			1	0.97420	2	0.8977	2	0.9360	1.41	0.812	0.857
			1.2	1.28423	2	1.1981	2	1.2412	1.41	0.692	0.725
			1.5	1.81400	2	1.6997	2	1.7569	1.41	0.650	0.679
			1.7	2.13897	1	2.0443	1	2.0916	0.71	0.910	0.938
			2	2.54785	1	2.4929	1	2.5204	0.71	0.442	0.449

Table 16: Comparison results for CoFe 0.2 using 12 strips at 23 °C and at frequencies between 400 Hz and 5000 Hz.

N_s	T (°C)	f (Hz)	J (T)	LAB 1		LAB 2		x_{ref} (W/kg)	$u(x_{\text{ref}})$ (W/kg)	E_n	
				X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$			LAB 1	LAB 2
12	23	400	0.1	0.23323	1.5	0.2178	1.5	0.2255	1.06	0.908	0.951
			0.15	0.51494	1.7	0.4754	1.7	0.4952	1.20	0.933	0.985
			0.2	0.87907	1.8	0.8081	1.8	0.8436	1.27	0.928	0.982
			0.35	2.27362	1.7	2.1082	1.7	2.1909	1.20	0.884	0.930
			0.5	3.93159	1.7	3.6557	1.7	3.7937	1.20	0.852	0.895
			1	10.68358	1.7	10.2830	1.7	10.4833	1.20	0.453	0.465
			1.2	13.92330	1.5	13.8030	1.5	13.8631	1.06	0.118	0.118
			1.5	19.83477	1.2	20.3548	1.2	20.0948	0.85	0.444	0.436
			1.7	25.47411	1.2	25.6924	1.2	25.5833	0.85	0.146	0.145
			2.0	33.41254	0.5	33.5941	0.50	33.5033	0.35	0.222	0.221
		1000	0.1	0.73345	1.8	0.6738	1.8	0.7036	1.27	0.935	0.990
			0.15	1.62377	1.8	1.4938	1.8	1.5588	1.27	0.920	0.972
			0.2	2.78732	1.8	2.5772	1.8	2.6823	1.27	0.866	0.912
			0.35	7.10914	1	6.7915	1.05	6.9581	0.72	0.867	0.954
			0.5	12.29269	1	11.7708	1.05	12.0445	0.72	0.823	0.905
		2000	0.1	1.85821	1.5	1.7711	1.5	1.8147	1.06	0.643	0.664
			0.15	3.77927	1	3.9175	1.05	3.8450	0.72	0.700	0.730
			0.2	6.75266	1	6.7356	1.05	6.7445	0.72	0.049	0.052
			0.35	17.53878	1	17.4090	1.05	17.4771	0.72	0.143	0.153
			0.50	30.81465	0.75	30.7293	1.05	30.7858	0.61	0.048	0.076
		5000	0.1	7.30362	1	7.4677	1.05	7.3816	0.72	0.431	0.453
			0.15	15.88751	1	16.1074	1.05	15.9921	0.72	0.266	0.281

Table 17: Comparison results for CoFe 0.2 using 12 strips at 50 °C and at frequencies between 400 Hz and 5000 Hz.

N_s	T (°C)	f (Hz)	J (T)	LAB 1		LAB 2		x_{ref} (W/kg)	$u(x_{\text{ref}})$ (W/kg)	E_n	
				X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$			LAB 1	LAB 2
12	50	400	0.1	0.24989	3	0.2177	3	0.2338	2.12	0.896	0.982
			0.15	0.55437	3	0.4850	3	0.5197	2.12	0.869	0.950
			0.2	0.94742	3	0.8314	3	0.8894	2.12	0.850	0.927
			0.35	2.41883	2.5	2.1868	2.5	2.3028	1.77	0.796	0.851
			0.5	4.12351	2	3.7968	2	3.9601	1.41	0.819	0.866
			1	11.32805	2	10.7928	2	11.0604	1.41	0.486	0.502
			1.2	14.76777	0.5	14.4185	0.5	14.5931	0.35	0.969	0.985
			1.5	20.87696	0.5	21.1024	0.5	20.9897	0.35	0.440	0.437
			1.7	26.53298	0.5	26.2928	0.5	26.4129	0.35	0.370	0.372
			2.0	34.12434	0.5	34.0397	0.5	34.0820	0.35	0.101	0.102
		1000	0.1	0.77393	2.8	0.6835	2.8	0.7287	1.98	0.868	0.943
			0.15	1.73194	2.7	1.5389	2.7	1.6354	1.91	0.858	0.928
			0.2	2.96634	2.2	2.6756	2.2	2.8210	1.56	0.924	0.990
			0.35	7.53275	1.5	7.0634	1.5	7.2981	1.06	0.857	0.894
			0.5	13.02753	1.5	12.2772	1.5	12.6523	1.06	0.791	0.823
		2000	0.1	1.87874	1.2	1.7826	1.2	1.8307	0.85	0.877	0.909
			0.15	4.14870	1	4.0034	1.05	4.0796	0.72	0.678	0.741
			0.2	7.06635	1	6.9291	1.05	7.0011	0.72	0.375	0.406
			0.35	18.30789	1	17.9684	1.05	18.1464	0.72	0.358	0.387
			0.50	32.13550	0.75	31.8294	1.05	32.0321	0.61	0.167	0.262
		5000	0.1	7.15282	1	7.4616	1.05	7.2997	0.72	0.826	0.857
			0.15	15.49217	1	16.2470	1.05	15.8512	0.72	0.931	0.963

Table 18: Comparison results for CoFe 0.2 using 12 strips at 100 °C and at frequencies between 400 Hz and 5000 Hz.

N_s	T (°C)	f (Hz)	J (T)	LAB 1		LAB 2		x_{ref} (W/kg)	$u(x_{\text{ref}})$ (W/kg)	E_n	
				X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$			LAB 1	LAB 2
12	100	400	0.1	0.26227	3.5	0.2239	3.5	0.2431	2.47	0.874	0.971
			0.15	0.58973	3.5	0.5034	3.5	0.5465	2.47	0.875	0.972
			0.2	1.00837	3.5	0.8654	3.5	0.9369	2.47	0.847	0.937
			0.35	2.52386	3	2.2822	3	2.4030	2.12	0.662	0.708
			0.5	4.31270	3	3.9647	3	4.1387	2.12	0.556	0.588
			1	11.86625	2	11.2813	2	11.5738	1.41	0.507	0.525
			1.2	15.42370	0.75	15.0231	0.75	15.2234	0.53	0.710	0.722
			1.5	21.95357	0.5	21.8258	0.5	21.8897	0.35	0.238	0.239
			1.7	27.15741	0.5	26.9017	0.55	27.0417	0.37	0.343	0.392
			2.0	34.82420	0.5	34.6357	0.45	34.7200	0.33	0.249	0.217
		1000	0.1	0.79328	2.8	0.7003	2.8	0.7468	1.98	0.871	0.946
			0.15	1.78273	2.7	1.5878	2.7	1.6853	1.91	0.842	0.909
			0.2	3.03776	2.2	2.7642	2.2	2.9010	1.56	0.848	0.903
			0.35	7.85499	1.5	7.3115	1.5	7.5833	1.06	0.952	0.999
			0.5	13.51046	1.5	12.7396	1.5	13.1250	1.06	0.784	0.815
		2000	0.1	2.02998	2.2	1.8394	2.2	1.9347	1.56	0.885	0.945
			0.15	4.52679	2	4.1605	2	4.3437	1.41	0.837	0.885
			0.2	7.68509	1.5	7.2081	1.5	7.4466	1.06	0.853	0.891
			0.35	18.93021	1.05	18.5996	1.05	18.7649	0.74	0.340	0.345
			0.50	33.31453	1.05	33.1022	1.05	33.2084	0.74	0.124	0.125
		5000	0.1	7.49770	1	7.4558	1.05	7.4778	0.72	0.108	0.115
			0.15	16.23579	1	16.4129	1.05	16.3200	0.72	0.210	0.222

Table 19: Comparison results for CoFe 0.2 using 12 strips at 155 °C and at frequencies between 400 Hz and 5000 Hz.

N_s	T (°C)	f (Hz)	J (T)	LAB 1		LAB 2		x_{ref} (W/kg)	$u(x_{\text{ref}})$ (W/kg)	E_n	
				X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$			LAB 1	LAB 2
12	155	400	0.1	0.2643	3.5	0.2254	3.5	0.2449	2.47	0.881	0.980
			0.15	0.5818	3.2	0.5037	3.2	0.5427	2.26	0.875	0.963
			0.2	0.9888	3	0.8637	3	0.9262	2.12	0.879	0.961
			0.35	2.5109	2	2.2862	2.00	2.3985	1.41	0.927	0.987
			0.5	4.2890	1.5	3.9970	1.5	4.1430	1.06	0.937	0.982
			1	11.8814	1	11.4640	1	11.6727	0.71	0.721	0.739
			1.2	15.4629	0.5	15.3585	0.45	15.4052	0.33	0.310	0.271
			1.5	22.1028	0.5	22.2489	0.90	22.1373	0.44	0.117	0.251
			1.7	27.1259	0.5	27.2457	0.65	27.1704	0.40	0.129	0.182
			2.0	34.3018	1.7	36.9935	1.7	35.6476	1.20	0.930	0.884
		1000	0.1	0.8128	3	0.7096	3	0.7612	2.12	0.882	0.966
			0.15	1.8282	3	1.6011	3	1.7146	2.12	0.863	0.943
			0.2	3.2069	3.1	2.7844	3.1	2.9957	2.19	0.887	0.974
			0.35	7.9559	1.5	7.4259	1.5	7.6909	1.06	0.916	0.960
			0.5	13.6227	1	12.9984	1.05	13.3258	0.72	0.889	0.979
		2000	0.1	2.0397	2.1	1.8546	2.1	1.9471	1.48	0.895	0.954
			0.15	4.5418	2	4.1795	2	4.3606	1.41	0.825	0.872
			0.2	7.7041	1.5	7.2494	1.5	7.4767	1.06	0.811	0.844
			0.35	18.9211	1	18.8506	1.05	18.8876	0.72	0.072	0.077
		5000	0.1	7.43862	1	7.6066	1.05	7.5185	0.72	0.433	0.456
0.15	16.26896		1	16.6887	1.05	16.4686	0.72	0.495	0.519		

5 Summary and conclusions

This technical report was produced by NPL in collaboration with INRIM and UNOTT. After the evaluation of the data, it was found that:

- For the Si-Fe 95% of the measurements performed had a standard deviation between NPL and INRIM of less than 1%, while the remaining measurements were between 1.1% and 1.7%
- For the Co-Fe, 73% of the measurements performed had a standard deviation between NPL and INRIM of less than 1.5%, while the remaining measurements were less than 2.5%.

After the evaluation of the data in agreement with the rules of EURAMET the agreement of the comparison is very good. This report also confirmed that the results are consistent with the declared uncertainty.

6 References

- [1] IEC 60404-2:1996/AMD1:2008/COR1:2018: Magnetic Materials – Part 2: Methods of measurement of magnetic properties of electrical steel strip and sheet by means of an Epstein Frame.
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- [3] IEC 60404-3:2022: Magnetic materials – Part 3: Methods of measurement of the magnetic properties of electrical steel strip and sheet by means of a single sheet tester.
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- [5] M. G. Cox: “The evaluation of key comparison data”, *Metrologia*, vol. 39, no. 6, 2002.
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